

5-Amino-4-cyano-1-diphenylmethylimidazole (1b) : To the DMF-POCl₃ complex (DMF 8 ml, POCl₃ 1.6 ml, 13 mmol) was added **1a** (2.2 g, 7.5 mmol) in one lot and the resulting solution stirred in an ice-bath for 45 min and at room temperature for 1 h. The resulting viscous mass was poured onto crushed ice (15 g) and basified with excess of aqueous ammonia. The yellow product was collected by filtration, washed well with ice-water, dried and crystallised from ethanol (1.5 g, 75%), m.p. 199–200° (Found : C, 74.37; H, 5.08; N, 20.47. C₁₇H₁₄N₄ requires : C, 74.45; H, 5.10; N, 20.43%; ν_{\max} 3 400, 3 190 (NH₂) and 2 220 cm⁻¹ (C≡N).

4-Amino-5-carboxamido-3-methyl-1-phenacylimidazolium bromide (2) : A mixture of **1c**¹ (1.4 g, 10 mmol) and phenacylbromide (2.2 g, 11 mmol) in DMF (3 ml) was refluxed for 45 min and the mixture was cooled. The resulting solid was washed well with acetone, dried and recrystallised from water (2.3 g, 68%), m.p. 249–50° (Found : C, 46.14; H, 4.30; N, 16.66. C₁₃H₁₃N₄O₂Br requires : C, 46.15; H, 4.40; N, 16.56%; ν_{\max} 3 350, 3 100 (NH₂) and 1 660 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-d₆, D₂O) 3.68 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.12 (2H, s, CH₂COPh), 7.44–7.84 (5H, m, ArH) and 8.88 (1H, s, C₅-H).

Action of alkali on 2 : A solution of **2** (0.4 g, 1.1 mmol) in 2% aqueous sodium hydroxide (4 ml, 2 mmol) was refluxed for 10 min and cooled. The resulting solid was recrystallised from water to afford **1c** (superimposable ir spectrum).

9-Diphenylmethylhypoxanthine (3) : A mixture of **1a** (0.5 g, 1.7 mmol) and formamide (6 ml) was heated in an oil-bath at 180° for 1.5 h. The mixture was then cooled to room temperature and diluted with water. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol; yield nearly quantitative, m.p. 267–68° (Found : C, 71.61; H, 4.64; N, 18.44. C₁₈H₁₄N₄O requires : C, 71.52; H, 4.63; N, 18.54%).

7-Diphenylmethylimidazo[4,5-d][1,2,3]triazine-4(3H)-one (4) : To a thoroughly cooled suspension of **1a** (1.46 g, 5 mmol) in 1 : 1 aqueous HCl (25 ml) was added a solution of sodium nitrite (0.7 g, 10 mmol) in water (8 ml) in one lot with stirring. The mixture was stirred in an ice-bath for 15 min when a clear solution was obtained. The solution was then allowed to attain room temperature when a solid began to separate. After keeping it at room temperature for 1 h, the resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to afford **4** (0.75 g, 50%), m.p. 184–85° (Found : C, 67.38; H, 4.38; N, 23.20. C₁₇H₁₃N₅O requires : C, 67.32; H, 4.29; N, 23.10%).

7-Methyl-9-diphenylmethylhypoxanthinium toluene-sulphonate (5) : A mixture of **3** (1.5 g, 5 mmol) and methyl toluene-*p*-sulphonate (1 g, 5.3 mmol) in DMF (2 ml) was refluxed for 45 min. The mixture was then cooled and triturated with ethyl acetate. The resulting sticky mass was dissolved in minimum amount of methanol and kept at -5° for several days when crystals of **5** separated out (1 g, 40%),

which was recrystallised from methanol-ethyl acetate, m.p. 224–25° (Found : C, 63.83; H, 4.88; N, 11.40. C₂₈H₂₄N₄O₄S requires : C, 63.93; H, 4.91; N, 11.57%).

4-Diphenylmethylamino-5-(N-methylformylamino)-1H,6H-pyrimidine-6-one (6) : A solution of **5** (0.2 g, 0.4 mmol) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%, 2.6 ml) was heated on a steam-bath for 1 h. The mixture was then cooled and acidified with acetic acid. The formyl derivative separated out was collected by filtration, dried and crystallised from ethyl acetate, the yield being nearly quantitative, m.p. 236–37° (Found : C, 68.29; H, 5.28; N, 16.73. C₁₉H₁₈N₄O₂ requires : C, 68.26; H, 5.38; N, 16.76%).

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Synthesis of New Substituted Chloroenamines from *N*-Methyl-2-chloroacetoacetamide†

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In continuation of our earlier studies on the synthesis of new enamines from *N*-methylacetamide², we report herein the synthesis of the 1-chloro-2-(aryl/aralkylamino)-*N*-methylcrotonamides (Scheme 1).

R = Aryl and aralkylamines

Scheme 1

The starting compound *N*-methyl-2-chloroacetoacetamide (**1**) was obtained by the chlorination of *N*-methylacetoacetamide². A number of 1-chloro-2-(aryl/aralkylamino)-*N*-methylcrotonamides (**3**) have been prepared according to the methods described earlier¹ by reacting **1** with aryl- and aralkylamines (**2**) in dry benzene or toluene. The structures of

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C B.p. °C/mm	Yield %	Mol. formula	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	δ
1.	C ₆ H ₅	89–90/ 0.2 mm	47	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O	3 230 (NH), 1 610 (C=C), 1 580 (C=O), 725 (Cl)	(CDCl ₃) 2.12 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.78–2.85 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, N-CH ₃), 5.80 (1H, b, NH), 6.80–7.10 (5H, m, ArH), 11.05 (1H, b, NH)
2.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	198–200	57	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O	3 310 (NH), 1 605 (C=C), 1 580 (C=O), 725 (Cl)	(CDCl ₃) 2.10 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.80 (3H, s, p-CH ₃ -ArH), 2.80–2.90 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, N-CH ₃), 5.80 (1H, b, NH), 6.81–7.31 (4H, m, ArH), 11.10 (1H, b, NH)
3.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	98–99	58	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O	3 340 (NH), 1 600 (C=C), 1 580 (C=O), 820 (Cl)	(CCl ₄) 2.10 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.81–2.90 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, N-CH ₃), 6.20 (1H, b, NH), 6.90–7.40 (4H, m, ArH), 11.80 (1H, b, NH)
4.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	128–30	54	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂	3 425 (OH), 3 220 (OH), 1 610 (C=O), 1 580 (C=O), 725 (Cl)	(CDCl ₃) 2.10 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.80–2.90 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, N-CH ₃), 5.75 (1H, b, NH), 6.70–7.10 (4H, m, ArH), 7.40 (1H, s, OH-ArH), 11.05 (1H, b, NH)
5.	C ₆ H ₅ OH	68–69	52	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O	3 320 (NH), 1 620 (C=C), 1 552 (C=O), 730 (Cl)	(CDCl ₃) 1.95 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.65–2.75 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, N-CH ₃), 4.30–4.40 (2H, d, CH ₂), 6.01 (1H, b, NH), 7.15–7.35 (5H, m, ArH), 10.70 (1H, b, NH)
6.	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄ OH	113–14	50	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O	3 342 (NH), 1 615 (C=C), 1 575 (C=O), 800 (Cl)	(CCl ₄) 1.90 (3H, s, p-CH ₃ -ArH), 2.35 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.85–2.95 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, N-CH ₃), 4.55 (2H, s, CH ₂ -ArH), 6.8 (1H, b, NH), 7.20–7.30 (4H, m, ArH), 9.80 (1H, b, NH)
7.	C ₆ H ₅ CH(OH) ₂	63–64	50	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O	3 340 (NH), 1 600 (C=C), 1 590 (CONH), 745 (Cl)	(CCl ₄) 1.45–1.55 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, α -CH ₃), 1.90 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.80–2.85 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, N-CH ₃), 4.40–4.70 (1H, q, J 6 Hz, CH-CH ₃), 6.05 (1H, b, NH), 7.25 (5H, m, ArH), 10.80 (1H, b, NH)
8.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ CH ₂	82–83	51	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O	3 340 (NH), 1 615 (C=C), 1 520 (C=O), 470 (Cl)	(CCl ₄), 1.95 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.80–2.90 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, N-CH ₃), 2.85 (2H, m, CH ₂), 3.3 (2H, d, CH ₂ -ArH), 5.9 (1H, b, NH), 7.20 (5H, m, ArH), 10.2 (1H, b, NH)
9.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH(CH ₃)	139–40	45	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O	3 280 (NH), 1 600 (C=C), 1 650 (C=O), 750 (Cl)	(CCl ₄) 1.20–1.30 (3H, d, CH ₃), 1.90 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.85–2.95 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, N-CH ₃), 3.31–3.60 (1H, q, CH-CH ₃), 2.51–2.80 (4H, m, CH ₂ CH ₂), 5.60 (1H, b, NH), 7.10–7.30 (5H, m, ArH), 9.90 (1H, b, NH)

*Satisfactory C, H and N analyses were obtained.

the compounds were confirmed by elemental analysis, ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

Experimental

The previous publication¹ describes details of the instruments.

Condensation of *N*-methyl-2-chloroacetamide (1) with aryl and aralkylamines (2): To a solution of

N-methyl-2-chloroacetamide (0.1 mol) and the aryl or aralkylamines (0.1 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) was added *p*-toluenesulphonic acid as a catalyst (0.005 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed with azeotropic removal of water. After removal of the solvent, the resulting product was purified by crystallisation from ether or petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Substitution of chlorine atom of *N*-methyl-2-chloroacetoacetamide (**1**) by a nucleophile is not possible because of presence of mesomeric anion of *N*-methyl-2-chloroacetoacetamide (**1**). Probably, the negative charge on both the carbonyl oxygens makes carbon-2 atom as an anion. Therefore, a nucleophilic substitution is possible on the carbonyl carbon atom to give the corresponding chloro enamines.

From the pmr spectra it was seen that the chloro enamines (**3**) were a mixture of (*Z*)- and (*E*)-isomers. Only (*Z*)-isomers of the compounds (sl. nos. 1–9) were isolated from the total product.

In the ir spectra of the chloro enamines (sl. nos. 1–9) the double bond stretching appears as a strong band at 1600–1620 cm^{-1} . The high extinction coefficient for this absorption may be attributed to the overlap between the electron pair on the nitrogen atom and the π -electrons of the double bond.

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Synthesis of Azomethines of Anthrone

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A new series of azomethines have been prepared by condensing anthrone with different primary amines, *o*-aminophenol and *p*-aminobenzoic acid (**1**) and (ii) nitrosonaphthols (**2**). A new compound 10-*p*-aminobenzylidene anthrone was also synthesised which was condensed with aldehydes and ketones to give one more new series of azomethines (**3**). Anticancer activity of all the compounds was studied.

Experimental

The m.p.s. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The structures were supported by elemental analysis and ir spectra (KBr).

Azomethines of the anthrone (1): The compounds were prepared from different primary amines, *o*-aminophenol and *p*-aminobenzoic acid (Table 1). Equimolar (0.01 mol) quantities of the anthrone and the respective primary amine or *o*-aminophenol or *p*-aminobenzoic acid taken in methanol or ethanol (25–30 ml) and glacial acetic acid (2–3 drops), were refluxed for 3 h and then allowed to cool overnight. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from methanol or ethanol; ν_{max} 1660 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Azomethines of the anthrone (2): The compounds were prepared from α - and β -nitrosonaphthols. Equimolar (0.01 mol) quantities of the anthrone and the respective nitrosonaphthol (prepared by standard methods¹) in methanol or ethanol (25–30 ml) were refluxed for 3 h. It was then poured hot on crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from 30% aqueous ethanol; ν_{max} 1660 (C=N) and 1680 cm^{-1} (C=O) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Ar/R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1a	C_6H_5-	202	70	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}$
1b	$p\text{-NO}_2-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	167	65	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$
1c	$o\text{-CH}_3-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	169	67	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}$
1d	$o\text{-OCH}_3-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	212	65	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$
1e	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CH}_2-$	225	55	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}$
1f	Naphthyl	194	65	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}$
1g	$o\text{-OH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	192	70	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}$
1h	$p\text{-HOOC}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	168	60	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$

